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PERCEPTUAL SYMBOL SYSTEMS REPRESENTATION ON COGNITIVE ARCHITECTURES.

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Abstract

This paper presents analysis of issues pertaining to the perceptual symbol mappings within the context of developing cognitive architecture (Motivational and CRIBB). I will consider Barasalou's theory of a perceptual Symbol systems, and its implications to computer science field. How the brain can capture images, What extent they can be stored and how they can be represented. I intended to investigate a simulator that produces limitless simulations by using proprioception (e.g Object shape) and the introspection (Changing Colour, intensity) within a particular environment. CRIBB (Children reasoning about intentions, Beliefs and Behaviour) is a computational model of belief-desire reasoning. The connectionist networks describes the connection between the names and objects that give rise to their sensory projections and their icons.

Keywords-Perception, symbol systems, Cognitive Architecture

INTRODUCTION

Bertrand Russell (1919b)[2], defines as "The habit of abstract pursuits makes learned men much inferior to the average in the power of visualization, and much more exclusively occupied with words in their thinking".

According to Liz [11] the eye is like a camera. It lets light in through the cornea, which is like a camera's aperture. The amount of light allowed

in is controlled by the pupil, which opens and closes a bit like a shutter. The light focuses on the retina, which sends the image to the brain, acting as film would in order to record the light (the photo itself). The distinction between a recording system and a conceptual system is central to this task (Dretske, 1995; Haugeland, 1991).

Perceptually based theories of knowledge are typically construed as recording systems. A recording system captures physical information by creating attenuated (not exact) copies of it, as exemplified by photographs, videotapes, and audiotapes. Notably, a recording system does not interpret what each part of a recording contains - it simply creates an attenuated copy. For example, a photo of a picnic simply records the light present at each point in the scene without interpreting the types of entities present.[2]

The Brain integrates and stores experiences, which could be previous classifications or associations of input data. In the sense it self organizes experience. The brain considers new experiences in the context of stored Experiences. This often requires a type of high level, symbolic, or iconic matching ability, as well as a means to "index" stored fast experiences from different view points. This suggests a context-addressable structure[10]. In

contrast, a conceptual system interprets the entities in a recording. In perceiving a picnic, the human conceptual system might construe perceived individuals as instances of tree, table, and watermelon, eat,above, and so forth.

To accomplish this, the conceptual system binds specific tokens in perception (i.e., individuals) to knowledge for general types of things in memory (i.e., concepts). Clearly, a system that only records perceptual experience cannot construe individuals in this manner--it only records them in the holistic context of an undifferentiated event[2].In contrast to the modern views, it is relatively straightforward to imagine how Cognition could be inherently perceptual. A perceptual state arises in sensory-motor systems. A perceptual state can contain two components: An unconscious neural representation of physical input, and an optional conscious experience.Once a perceptual state arises, a subset of it is extracted via selective attention and stored permanently in long term memory[12].

According to Barasalou's Perceptual symbols are modal and analogical. They are modal because they are represented in the same system as the perceptual states that produced them[4]. Perception is indeed a fundamental psychological process, and a very remarkable one. Its success in providing us with accurate information about the characteristics of the world around with us is an index of its power,

I.

Fig.1 Perceptual representations

The basic assumption underlying perceptual symbol systems: Subsets of perceptual states in sensory-motor systems are extracted and stored in long-term memory to function as symbols. As a result, the internal structure of these symbols is modal, and they are analogically related to the perceptual states that produced them.[2]

Barasalou[2] explained as, On perceiving a chair, information is extracted from Perceptual representations and transferred to memory. Once in memory, these extractions function

symbolically, standing for referents in the world and entering into all Forms of symbolic computation. Most importantly, these symbols are modal and analogical.

Barasalou[5] claims that,These symbols are modal because they have the same structure as perceptual states.These symbols are analogical because their structure is Informative and similarity between them corresponds to similarity between perceptual states.

2. The CRIBB Model

Fig 2. CRIBB architecture.

Wahl and Spada, (2000)[22] defines, the CRIBB(Children Reasoning about Intentions, beliefs and behaviour) is a computer model , it simulates knowledge and inference processes of a child solving problems. (The CRIBB architecture (fig. 2) consists of representations, inference schemata and a consistency mechanism. Representations (rectangular boxes in Fig. 2) fall into two main categories in CRIBB, primary and secondary representations. Primary representations consist of the systems own beliefs about the situation, the behaviour of others and facts about the physical world[15].Secondary representations consist of the systems beliefs about mental states. These include another ' s perceptions, beliefs, intentions and the systems prior to false beliefs. The consistency mechanism detects and resolves contradictions in the system ' s beliefs. Any beliefs deemed false become secondary representations[15, 16].

The CRIBB (Children ' s Reasoning about Intentions, Beliefs and Behavior) model was designed to investigate the belief-desire reasoning model in young children [21]. The model describes that a persons actions can be explained by there beliefs and desires. Beliefs can be derived from perceptions and previously held beliefs. For example a person may believe that their wife purchased some milk from the

shops and then saw her put something in a fridge. This may lead to the belief that there is a milk in the fridge. Desires can be derived from emotions and physiology, the person may be hungry and like to drink milk and therefore want the milk. The combination of the person's beliefs and desires may lead it to action which in turn leads to a reaction. The person may open the fridge and be disappointed when it discovers that there is no milk. When CRIBB is given a proposition, a belief is inferred from this. The Consistency of the belief is checked with existing set of beliefs[16]. If no contradiction is found then it is added to the belief set.

For example

$$B: = \{ \sim p \}$$

$$P: = \{ r, s, \sim s, q, \}$$

$$P \otimes B \rightarrow B'$$

$$B' := \{ r, s, q, p \}$$

$$B \otimes D \rightarrow D'$$

$$D' \otimes I \rightarrow I'$$

Where B is the existing belief set and P is perception set, the new set B' contains The systems's new belief set with all possible contradictions resolved[20]. D is the desire set, the new set D' contains the systems's new desire set.

I is the the intention and I' is the new intention set. The inference schemata (ellipses in fig. 2) are based on the Belief-Desire reasoning scheme in figure 2.. Perception-belief inferences represent knowledge about the relationship of perception and belief. If a person perceives X then person believes X. Fact-time and belief-time inferences deal with facts and beliefs along a time scale. If a fact/belief is true at t 1 then that fact/belief is also true at t 2 unless there is information

2.4.Perceptual Symbol mappings

Harnard (Harnard,1990)[16] assess that, The categorical representations cannot be interpreted as "meaning" anything. It is true that they pick out the class of objects they "name," but the names do not have all the systematic properties of symbols and symbol systems described earlier.They are just an inert taxonomy. For

systematically it must be possible to combine and recombine them rulefully into propositions that can be semantically interpreted.

For example:

(1) Suppose the name "horse" is grounded by iconic and categorical representations, learned from experience, that reliably discriminate and identify horses on the basis of their sensory projections.

(2) Suppose "stripes" is similarly grounded.By considering the following category can be constituted out of these elementary categories by a symbolic description of category membership alone:

(3) "Zebra" = "horse" & "stripes". (This animal resembles a horse except of course it has black and white stripes)

What is the representation of a zebra? It is just the symbol string "horse & stripes." But because "horse" and "stripes" are grounded in their respective iconic and categorical representations, "zebra" inherits the grounding, through its grounded symbolic representation. In principle, someone who had never seen a zebra (but had seen and learned to identify horses and stripes) could identify a zebra on first acquaintance armed with this symbolic representation alone (plus the nonsymbolic -- iconic and categorical -- representations of horses and stripes that ground it)(Harnard,1990)Once one has the grounded set of elementary symbols provided by a taxonomy of names (and the iconic and categorical representations that give content to the names and allow them to pick out the objects they identify), the rest of the symbol strings of a natural language can be generated by symbol composition alone, and they will all inherit the intrinsic grounding of the elementary set. Hence, the ability to discriminate and categorize (and its underlying nonsymbolic representations) has led naturally to the ability to describe and to produce and respond to descriptions through symbolic representations(Barasalou,1999).

2.5. Interactions between perception and concepts:

One of primary research goals is to expand our understanding perception, Cognition and their interaction. The human conceptual system contains knowledge that supports all cognitive activities, including perception, memory, language and thought(Wade and swanston, 2001)The 'high level'[ex:-human] cognition is fundamentally grounded in our perceptual abilities.

This cognitive retain their connection to Perception. There are 2 different ideas about what concepts are like in cognitive Science, linguists and artificial intelligence researchers(Davis and Lewis).A common theme on this research on concept learning is that although they are abstract, the concepts are inherently connected to our perceptual world(Sorenson and gedney)

Concepts are causal relations between the world and environment(Brasalou,simmons,Barbey & Wilson,2003), Many of the devices that are used for analyzing world such as spatial Organization and selective attention are borrowed for more abstract Conceptual tasks involving language reasoning & decision making.Linguists and artificial intelligence researchers often stress the interrelations between concepts - concepts are defined in terms of their connections to other concepts in a system(Goldstone,1994).

Davis(2002) explains about human mind as, there is no central co coordinator in this generalized architecture. the apparent need for a central coordinator, arising out of the mind as an certain type of operating system With a central processor, is an illusion caused by a lack of understanding about the nature of attention in the human mind.

Davis(Davis and Lewis, 2003) also explained about the motivators as, motivators are problem-solving schemas which link internal and external 'reality'Involving perception of events and states representations and paths to modified States of affairs. The dynamic state of the motivator e.g. being considerd, nearing, completion etc.

Davis(Davis and Lewis, 2003) has identified 4 important specific factors which influences on motivators attention weighting. These are

(1)Importance(e.g natural, low, medium,high,unknown): This may be intrinsic or Based on associated processes, whether affective, cognitive or hybrid.

(2)Insistence: A heuristic value determining interrupt capabilities this value results from the affect Model and importance, intensity and urgency components.

(3)Intensity:-In effect the value of the affective system and processes associates with the difference between current and desired state of the motivation .

(4)Urgency Description: - how urgent is this descriptor this may be qualitative (e.g. low, high) quantitative(For ex- a time cost function). According to "percepts and concepts lab"(Goldstone, 1994) we can consider an illustrated ways that concepts influence our perception made by the perceptually manifestwd by Lee, conceived by Goldstone

- Attention Weighting
- Categorical Perception
- Dimensionalization
- Unitization
- Segmentation
- Assimilation and Contrast
- Differentiation
- Idealization
- Elaboration

Fig 2.5.1. Dimensionalization (Goldstone,1994).

This picture describes a perceptual dimensions (size, brightness, saturation, eccentricity) by witnessing variation along these dimensions. It tends to order objects by their value on dimensions that it created or already possess. Objects that are originally perceived holistically, without being decomposed into separate dimensions, come to be perceived analytically, in terms of their underlying dimensions.

Fig 2.5.2. Unitization(Goldstone, 1994).

Goldstone(1994) interpreted,if a group of shapes form a coherent, contiguous pattern and are often repeated together, a single chunk or unit will be formed by concatenating them together. He also indicated, unitization is the opposite of dimensionalization and segmentation. Whereas these latter mechanisms break down an object into parts or dimensions, unitization creates a

single unit from multiple parts that occur together.

Fig 2.5.3 Segmentation(Goldstone, 1994)

This naturally sees objects as being composed out of parts. Instead of perceiving indivisible objects, it perceives objects in terms of their labelled or categorized parts. We break objects into parts that we have learned are relevant or important..

Fig 2.5.4. Assimilation and Contrast(Goldstone, 1994).

this distort the dimension values of an object so that they become more like the values typically seen for the object's category (assimilation), or less like the values seen for contrasting categories (contrast). If an object is categorized into a group, its appearance is assimilated toward the group. If an object is not categorized in the group, then its appearance is distorted away from the group.

DIFFERENTIATION

Fig 2.5.5. Differentiation(Goldstone, 1994).

With expertise or practise, differences are noticed between objects that were once thought to be Identical.

IDEALIZATION

Fig 2.5.6. Idealization(Goldstone, 1994).

Objects are often simplified so as to capture the basic essence of the underlying concept.

ELABORATION

Fig 2.5.7. Elaboration(Goldstone, 1994).

The "filling in" of perceptual details according to what we know of the object. In some ways, this is the opposite of *idealization* in that it involves creating richer, rather than more impoverished, representations.

IV. IMPLEMENTING LEARNING IN FUNGUS WORLD TESTBED

1. **Encounter:** Learning process begins at the very start of agent's life, but how knowledgeable it gets depends on how agent looks at suspicious things, when and at what instance it encounters with resources, decisions taken based on its available knowledge, emotional level and likewise.
2. **Identify:** Once it encounters, it has to identify. Agent succeeds in identifying then learning process takes place which is described in next step. On failure, it queries

Metacontrol with 5 agents comparing Perceptual level 5 V/s

Graph 1 Performance of SMCA lower levels to higher level agents

This experiment is conducted for observing an effect of perceptual range on each agent or

3. **Act:** Moving forward towards goal oriented behavior. Making predictions on which direction to choose by considering finite state machine.

VI. SIMULATED RESULTS

Simulated result shows that Learner demonstrates the potential to learn as when it

environment to get the type, then store the type for later use (if again agent comes across this resource, it can use this as prior knowledge). By this, agent could experience some affect from consumption of resources then agent has to learn from this experience.

Learn: Agent performs Q Learning with extended care by check decision making parameters, generating Learning rate and discount factors values by considering agent's internal states. i.e. emotional level-desire, intention, metabolism rate. Also get the reward value from environment. Calculate Q value using Learning rate and discount factors generated which also depends upon resource that it encountered. Thus Q Learning Algorithm is applied and corresponding values for Resource types are updated.

agent's performance. The experiment is conducted for two different situations. Perceptual range of 5 :10 with 5agents Perceptual range of 5 :10 with 10 agents

Life expectancy and resource collection are two metrics used in this experiment. The life expectancy is defined as the survival of agents in a testbed for fixed energy or nutrients. Resource collection is defined as the number of resources such as ore, golden ore and crystal are collected in given a time cycle.

Based on the results obtained in these experiments (graphs from section 1.1 and 1.2) the life expectancy of perceptual range of 10 level agents (society of agents) has higher expectancy than perceptual range of 5 level agents. Perceptual range of 10 level agents managed to have higher energy level after the maximum cycles (i.e.25 cycles), as compare to perceptual range of 5 level agents (10 to 20% more).The perceptual range of 10 level agents managed to collect more number of pieces of ore and crystals (resources) collected after the maximum cycles (i.e.25 cycles), as compare to perceptual range of 5 level agents. It concludes that, the perceptual range or perceptual level increases the agent's belief set for sensing in the environment. If the perceptual level increases the society of agent's performance also increases

encounters with the resources in its environment. Furthermore, observation of the activity of Learner shows a kind of personal selection that it makes in exhibiting an action. It also shows significant learningwhen its energy level is high, and with higher rewards. It does by increasing its learning rate. Being in bad emotional state, higher metabolic rate or lower energy level, agent seizes to learn as it lacks interest and decreases its learning rate

parameter, so that its intention is driven to find remedial measures or carry out its goal oriented task.

Experiments are conducted on agents in SMCAusing Fungus world testbed [1]. Agents from different levels of Architecture were employed for this experiment. In this experiment to show the effect of learning on an agent, we considered comparisons between reflexive agent, reactive agent, the reactive agent with inclusion of learning mechanism- learner and BDI agent.

The agents are experimented with same percentage (100%) life expectancy and resources (refer graph 1).

VII. CONCLUSION

This research paper illustrates how to implement learning with various parameters like metabolism rate, emotional state, previous knowledge, energy level and likewise. Making use of available SMCA model and fungus world testbed, simulated results showed that learning algorithms which make use of these parameters demonstrated resembles of animal-like learning behaviors. This also showed the enhancement of Reinforcement learning which showed that an infant can be brought about to be knowledgeable and further act intelligently. This research gives a new roadmap for connecting animal learning onto agents in virtual world.

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